

SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING AND STRUCTURAL DIFFERENCES IN ARRANGING INFORMATION

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola koreys va rus tillarida og‘zaki tarjima va strukturaviy farqlar masalalariga bag‘ishlangan. O‘rganilayotgan ikki tilning grammatik tuzilishining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, xatolar ko‘pincha tarkibiy xususiyatlarni yetarli darajada bilmaslik va jumla komponentlarining harakatchanligini o‘zgartirish qobiliyati tufayli tarjimada uchraydi. Koreys tili va rus tili o‘rtasidagi tarkibiy farq, ayniqsa ma‘lumotni tarjima qilishda nafaqat oxirida, balki bayonotning boshida ham bo‘lishi mumkin.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *koreys tili, rus tili, tarjima, talqin, tilshunoslik*

Аннотация: *Настоящая статья посвящена вопросам устного перевода и структурных различий в корейском и русском языках. Особенности грамматического строя двух исследуемых языков показывает, что в переводе чаще всего происходят ошибки из-за недостаточно знаний структурных особенностей и возможности варьировать подвижностью компонентов предложения. Структурное различие между корейским и русским языками, в особенности, при переводе информация может содержаться не только в конце, но и в начале высказывания.*

Ключевые слова: *корейский язык, русский язык, перевод, устный перевод, лингвистика*

Annotation: *This article focuses on the effect of structural differences between Korean and Russian language in simultaneous interpretation. The peculiarities of the grammatical structure of the two languages show that translation errors most often occur due to insufficient knowledge of structural features and the ability to vary the mobility of the components of the sentences. The structural differences between two languages are directly related to the process of arranging information in simultaneous interpretation.*

Key words: *Korean language, Russian language, translation, interpretation, linguistics*

In linguistics, branching refers to the shape of the parse trees that represent the structure of sentences.

Assuming that the language is being written or transcribed from left to right, parse tree that grow to the right is right-branching, and parse tree that grow to the left are left-branching [1, 390].

The structural difference between Korean and Russian and the corresponding information arrangement comes from the difference of branching direction. Russian language is a right-branching language whereas Korean language is a left-branching language that extends to the left.

Due to this difference, from the translator's point of view, in Russian language, the main information is obtained first, but in Korean language, it is encountered last.

Мы приняли и последовательно реализуем «дорожные карты» по укреплению промкооперации с Россией, Казахстаном, Беларусью и Кыргызстаном [2].

우리는 러시아, 카자흐스탄, 벨라루시, 키르기스스탄과의 산업 협력을 강화하기 위한 로드맵을 채택하고 지속적으로 구현하고 있습니다.

If we look at the verb phrase in the above Russian sentence, the main element of the sentence is the verb ‘приняли’ and ‘реализуем’.

From these verbs other elements of the words extend to the right. From the interpreter's point of view, we can hear the first part of the whole sentence ‘Мы приняли и последовательно реализуем’, and the last content can be inferred from the words ‘приняли и последовательно реализуем о том, что’.

That is, information processing that can compose a frame is first obtained, and then the specific content is filled in the frame.

Conversely, in Korean language, the following object sentence ‘러시아, 카자흐스탄, 벨라루시, 키르기스스탄과의 산업 협력을 강화하기 위한 로드맵을(road maps to strengthen industrial cooperation with Russia, Kazakhstan, Belarus and Kyrgyzstan)’ which has the specific meanings comes before the verb ‘채택하고 구현하고 있습니다.(adopted and are implementing)’.

Therefore the interpreter holds these specific contents in his memory, and based on this, information processing takes place in such a way that the frame given at the end of the sentence is gradually constructed.

The structural difference between Korean and Russian also appears in relative clause [3, 359].

In the case of relational clauses, as shown in the example below, the direction of information arrangement is also opposite between Russian language and Korean language.

Последовательная реализация этого основополагающего документа, который в полной мере отражает глубокие исторические традиции дружбы и взаимопонимания между российским и китайским народами, позволила вывести наши отношения на беспрецедентно высокий уровень [4].

러시아와 중국 인민 간의 우호와 상호 이해의 깊은 역사적 전통을 충분히 반영하는 이 기본 문서의 일관된 이행으로 양국의 관계는 전례 없는 높은 수준으로 발전하였습니다.

In the example above, the most important part in the Korean relative clause and Russian relative clause are ‘реализация этого основополагающего документа (문서의 이행, implementation of this basic document)’. The fact that the branching directions of relative clauses are completely opposite is clearly understood.

From the interpreter's point of view, in the case of Russian language, the core content is given first, so the structure can be easily grasped [5, 13].

In the Russian example above, the relative pronoun 'который' is placed at the beginning of the relative clause. We can understand the linguistic structure and its core by listening to only the first part of the entire information.

However, in the case of Korean language, the specific meaning of the 문서의 이행 (implementation of this basic document) can be known only after understanding the suffix of '-ㄴ' from the sentence '반영하는 (reflects)'.

Рассмотрение этого дела затянется ещё на несколько лет, что сохраняет так называемые владельческие риски, связанные непосредственно с решениями и положением руководителя компании, если оно будет передано в Верховный суд [6].

시간대별로 남김같은 행에 관한 논의는 몇년 더 지연될 것이며 이는 최고 경의 결정 및 직후 직접적으로 관련 수의 경의 방에 위를 가져올 수 있습니다

Similarly, if we look at adverb clauses, subordinate endings to mark the corresponding subordinate relationship at the end of the adverb clause in Korean language, but in Russian languages they use a method of placing conjunctions before adverb clauses.

If we suppose that the example sentence shown above is a situation of simultaneous interpretation, interpreter can use expression " -르 경우 " only after listening to the conditional adverb ' если ' in Russian.

In this case, there is a pause in the interpreting process, and there is a large difference between the speaker's utterance speed and the speaker's utterance, so it is impossible to maintain the simultaneity of the interpreter.

In the process of simultaneously interpreting from Russian language to Korean language, in order to interpret adverbial clauses naturally, the interpreter need to accurately grasp the flow of semantic development and logic, and to remember the link of the syntax.

This requires the interpreter's high level short-term memory skills, information processing skills, and logic skills.

The difference in branching direction between Korean language and Russian language as described above causes a big difference in the information processing.

In the case of Korean language, since the important element of a clause or a phrase is located at the end of the corresponding structure, the linguistic structure and predictability are low.

Such structural predictability difficulties in Korean language are not a serious problem in general conversation. Even if the translator predicts an incorrect linguistic structure, the error in information processing is resolved as soon as additional information is obtained.

However, in the case of simultaneous translation, in which the structure and content of a sentence are interpreted at the time and transferred to another language, the translator's incorrect prediction leads to an irreversible error.

Besides if interpreting is performed after waiting for the head content to appear, the flow of interpretation is unnaturally cut off and this can lead to a huge gap in interpretation. The structural difference between Korean

language and Russian language can cause great burden in simultaneous translating.

Hence, there is a need for a scientific and efficient strategy to solve the problems by specifically categorizing errors. In addition, it is necessary to prepare a framework according to the features of branching direction between the source language and the target language and effectively apply it to actual interpretation.

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